

Is the Stock Market More Profitable With the Uptick Rule than Without It?

Testing the Steady Gain Hypothesis

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Note: This is a rough draft. Please feel free to pass this along to others for review. Your comments and criticism would be most appreciated. Tom Arnold arnoldtk@mail.uc.edu

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In 2007, the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) removed rule 10a-1 of the Securities Exchange Act of 1934 from stock trading. Rule 10a-1, commonly referred to as the “uptick rule,” is a stock trading rule that had been in place since 1938. The uptick rule put price restrictions on short selling in order to protect investors from heavy losses in the stock market. The SEC had conducted an experiment in 2005 to determine the effects of removing the uptick rule, and the results of the SEC experiment had suggested that the stock market would be three times more profitable with the uptick rule than without it. The problem was that this finding had no theory to explain it. In this analysis, another test is made of the expected increase in profitability with the addition of price restrictions on short selling, and it was found that the market could be expected to be 2.5 to 2.66 times more profitable with the uptick rule than without it. The increase in profitability would amount to a gain of over one half of one Trillion dollars per year if the uptick rule were reinstated. The problem with a lack of theory to explain this difference still remains.

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Testing the Steady Gain Hypothesis

From time to time, there are scientific findings that occur that no one is expecting. Sometimes, unexpected findings can be explained away because they appear to fit neatly into another theory. When findings appear to fit another theory, they are often ignored. In this article, an exploration will be made of unexpected findings which seemed to fit the prevailing theory but could also fit a new theory. The prevailing hypothesis had suggested that the unexpected findings were a temporary anomaly. The new hypothesis contradicts the prevailing hypothesis. Which hypothesis is correct?

The findings in question were produced by the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) during a test to determine whether the removal of a stock trading rule, called the uptick rule, would have an effect on market profitability. The uptick rule places price restrictions on short selling, which is the practice of selling stock that one does not own. In a short sale, instead of selling actual stock, the short seller makes a promise to deliver stock at the sale price at a future date.

The SEC findings suggested that there would be a two percent loss in income from stock trading in six months if the price restrictions provided by the uptick rule were removed. The SEC findings were ignored because they were statistically insignificant and because they matched the prevailing theory of short selling. The prevailing theory of short selling, which will be called the overpricing hypothesis, states that there is a market equilibrium price, and gains in the present due to restrictions on short selling will be lost in the future when the market reverts back to its correct value.

An alternative hypothesis to the overpricing hypothesis was suggested in an article by Harman and Bar-Yam (2008).¹ The alternative hypothesis can be framed so that it states: “When a stock trading

¹ Harmon, Dion, & Bar-Yam, Yaneer (2008). Technical Report on SEC Uptick Repeal Pilot. Boston: New England Complex Systems Institute. <http://www.necsi.edu/research/UptickTechReport.pdf>.

rule called the “uptick rule” is in place, the stock market will be substantially more profitable.”² Their hypothesis, which will be called the steady gain hypothesis, makes a prediction that the stock market with the uptick rule in place will produce triple the profit that a stock market without the uptick rule in place will produce. The steady gain hypothesis contradicts the overpricing hypothesis. The overpricing hypothesis states that there can only be temporary gains due to restrictions on short selling. There does not appear to be a theory of how a steady gain without future offsetting losses could occur. Nonetheless, the steady gain hypothesis is an interesting one and certainly seems worthy of testing.

Background

The uptick rule, whose formal name is Rule 10a-1, is a stock trading rule that was put in place by the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) in 1938 in order to regulate short selling in U.S. stock markets.³ Short selling is a stock trading practice where stock brokers are allowed to sell stock that they do not own. The uptick rule placed a price restriction on short sales so that with the uptick rule in place, brokers cannot sell stock that they do not own at prices less than the current market price. The uptick rule was put in place to prevent large losses and there does not appear to be a theoretical mechanism that would explain why the uptick rule might enhance the profitability of the stock market.

The uptick rule was removed from stock trading in 2007.⁴ The SEC decision to remove the uptick rule from stock trading in 2007 has resulted in a debate over whether this was a wise decision.⁵ People who support the SEC decision to remove the uptick rule do not want price restrictions on short selling.

There are two various opinions held by opponents of price restrictions on short selling. Some

² Harmon & Bar-Yam actually suggested that the market will lose money without the uptick rule, but this is the same as saying that the market will make more money with the uptick rule.

³ SEC (1938). Rules for the regulation of short selling. Securities Exchange Act of 1934: Release No. 34-1548. Federal Register, 3: 213 (Jan. 26, 1938). <http://s63428.gridserver.com/wp-content/uploads/2009/04/uptickrule01-26-1938.pdf>

⁴ SEC (2007). Regulation SHO and Rule 10a-1: Final rule. Securities Exchange Act of 1934: Release No. 34-55970; File No. S7-21-06, Federal Register, 72, 36348 (July 3, 2007). <http://www.sec.gov/rules/final/2007/34-55970.pdf>

⁵ SEC (2009). Securities Exchange Act of 1934: Release No. 34-59748; File No. S7-08-09. Comments. <http://www.sec.gov/comments/s7-08-09/s70809.shtml>

opponents of the uptick rule argue that the uptick rule was not necessary because it has no effect on stock prices. Other opponents argue that the uptick rule was harming the efficiency of stock trading and causing stocks to become overpriced.

People in favor of the uptick rule argue that price restrictions on short selling are needed. Supporters of the uptick rule argue that unrestricted short selling causes lower profits and bigger swings in stock prices. Uptick rule supporters argue that price restrictions on short selling can help protect investors and make the market a safer place to invest.

The SEC decision to remove the uptick rule was made after the SEC did an experiment to determine whether removing the uptick rule would have a detrimental effect on stock trading. In 2005, the SEC removed the uptick rule from about one third of the stocks in the Russell 3000.⁶ The SEC left the uptick rule on the other two thirds of the Russell 3000 stocks. The Russell 3000 stocks with the uptick rule in place generated a little over 2% more income in six months than stocks without the uptick rule. The difference in income was statistically insignificant and was considered unimportant.

Harman and Bar-Yam argued that the 2% loss in income from removal of the uptick rule amounts to an annual loss of over 4% per year if the trend continued. A 4% loss assumes that the gain due to having an uptick rule in place will not be lost in the future. If they are correct, investors could be losing several hundred billion dollars per year because the uptick rule was removed.⁷ It would therefore appear to be highly important to determine whether these critics of the SEC decision to remove the uptick rule have a valid concern. Did the uptick rule cause higher profits and lower volatility from 1938

⁶ SEC (2007). Economic Analysis of the Short Sale Price Restrictions Under the Regulation SHO Pilot, Office of Economic Analysis, U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission, Feb. 06, 2007.
<http://www.sec.gov/news/studies/2007/regshopilot020607.pdf>

⁷ A 4% loss due to the removal of the uptick rule multiplied by the current market capitalization of the U.S. Stock market of around 12 Trillion dollars would amount to a loss of 480 Trillion dollars per year. The current market capitalization is provided by the Wilshire 5000 broad market index.
<http://web.wilshire.com/Indexes/Broad/Wilshire5000/>

to 2007? In other words, is the market losing hundreds of Billions of dollars per year by not having an uptick rule in place?

Harman and Bar-Yam argued that the 2% difference in income in six months between stocks with and without the uptick rule was statistically insignificant because the SEC had split their sample into two samples. One sample consisted of NASDAQ stocks and the other sample consisted of stocks traded on the New York and American Stock Exchanges (NYSE, AMEX). In both samples, the income was over 2% greater for stocks with the uptick rule in place, and the difference was statistically insignificant for both samples. When the samples were combined, the difference became statistically significant.

Harman and Bar-Yam argued that the 2.4% loss in income in six months reported for the listed stock sample in the SEC study becomes a 4.8% loss in one year. A 4.8% annual loss represents a huge loss in income from stock trading if one considers that the historical rate of return from stock trading since World War II has only been 7%. A loss of 4.8% would represent a loss of over two thirds of the income from stock trading.

To say that removing the uptick rule causes a loss is probably not the correct way to frame this hypothesis. Unrestricted short selling is the default condition and the price restrictions due to the uptick rule were added. In other words, the uptick rule places a restriction on the default condition of unrestricted short selling. Therefore, the steady gain hypothesis should state that the profits from stock trading will triple if price restrictions on short selling are put in place (2.2% vs. 7% is a 1-3 ratio). Although Harman & Bar-Yam did not call their assertion about predicted profits due to the uptick rule a hypothesis, I will call it the steady gain hypothesis. The formal statement of this hypothesis is: Price restrictions on short selling such as those provided by the uptick rule will cause a steady gain in the profits from stock trading.

A basic problem with the steady gain hypothesis is that it is completely inductive. It is derived from six months of data and makes a long term prediction. No mechanism is proposed and there are no

existing tests of the steady gain hypothesis over the long term. The steady gain hypothesis contradicts the overpricing hypothesis which states that a present gain will result in a future loss. At the very least, one would need to find another data set to test which hypothesis is correct. Before wasting any time trying to do more, it would seem that some sort of corroboration of the steady gain hypothesis is needed.

The steady gain hypothesis contradicts the overpricing hypothesis. The overpricing hypothesis states that a gain in value in the present will result in a loss in the future. Another way to state the overpricing hypothesis is “There Ain’t No Such Thing As A Free Lunch (TANSTAAFL).” The overpricing hypothesis states that stocks have an equilibrium price and temporary gains due to price restrictions will be followed by losses of equal magnitude at some future point in time. The overpricing hypothesis was proposed by Meeker (1932), who stated that the mode of selling can have no effect on the long term trend in stock prices.⁸ This theory states that, if stock market values grow faster because of the uptick rule, the values should fall by an equally large amount at a future date. Short selling is thought to produce a zero sum effect on the stock market. According to the overpricing hypothesis, restrictions on short selling should have no effect on the stock market.

Existing Research

Research that tests the overpricing hypothesis at the market level is rare. The SEC data provides the only experimental data comparing short selling with and without price restrictions. The analysis of the SEC data indicates that there is some question about whether there is a significant difference in income between stocks with and without the uptick rule. The SEC test does not cover a long enough time period to determine whether the overpricing hypothesis is valid.

⁸ Meeker, J. Edward (1932). *Short-selling*. New York: Harper & Brothers Publishers. Meeker did not use the term overpricing. The term overpricing is more recent, but the current meaning is similar to the concept proposed by meeker.

Meeker had suggested that markets with no short selling were likely to have larger size crashes than markets with short selling. This may be true, but this fact would not be expected to provide an indication of the differences due to markets with and without price restrictions. Markets with price restrictions still allow short selling.

Various studies have been done at the individual stock level to determine whether overpricing occurs in individual stocks.⁹ The typical finding is that restrictions on short selling can result in temporary gains, which are often accompanied by lower future returns. Overpricing studies also indicate that stocks that have higher levels of short selling have lower returns than stocks with lower levels of short selling. The net difference in overall returns between markets with and without short selling cannot be determined from these studies.

Which theory is correct? The steady gain hypothesis suggests that there will be no down side to price restrictions and that the uptick rule is a win-win proposition. There will be no future drop in value of an equal magnitude. The overpricing hypothesis states that a gain in stock market value due to price restrictions will result in a future loss. The only way to test which hypothesis is correct is to look at data of a sufficiently long time period so that the effects of the future losses can be determined.

A Quick Test of the Steady Gain Hypothesis

If the steady gain hypothesis were true, it would mean that the stock market would be substantially more profitable with the uptick rule than without it. How could this be tested? One possibility is to examine changes in the value of the Dow Jones Industrial Index (DOW). If the steady gain hypothesis were true, the annual gain in the DOW during the time period with the uptick rule in place should be about three times the annual gain when there was no uptick rule.

⁹ For example, see Jones, Charles M. & Lamont, Owen A. (2002). Short-Sale Constraints and Stock Returns. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 66: 207-239.

Data on daily close values for the DOW was obtained from the Dow Jones web site. The data covered the period from May, 1896 to the present day. The uptick rule was put in place on February 8th, 1938 and removed on July 5th, 2007. This would allow a quick before and after test to determine what the annual gains were during these periods. There were 42 years without the uptick rule and 69 years with the uptick rule. Using the formula for calculating annual gains,¹⁰ the results shown in Table 1 were found. The DOW gained only 2.63% per year when there were no restrictions on short selling and the DOW gained 6.99% when the uptick rule was in place. The ratio between these two numbers is 2.66 to 1, which is not quite the 3 to 1 ratio that was predicted from the six month data, but it was close. The difference in income was 4.37% per year, which was slightly smaller than the 4.78% difference found by the SEC, but not by much. At this rate, given a 12 Trillion dollar market capitalization, U.S. investors are still losing over half of a Trillion dollars per year without the uptick rule.

Table 1: Annual Percent Increase in the DOW for Periods Without and With the Uptick Rule

	Start Date	End Date	Start Value	End Value	Years	Percent Annual Increase
Without Uptick Rule	05/26/1896	02/07/1938	40.94	121.39	41.8	2.63%
With Uptick Rule	02/08/1938	07/03/2007	125.52	13577.30	69.3	6.99%

The problem with the method used above is that it is extremely sensitive to the choice of starting and ending dates. If one wanted to calculate the rate of growth from 5/26/1896 to 9/3/1929, the peak of the DOW before the decline that lead to the Great Depression, the average annual growth was 6.94%, which is almost identical to the rate of growth found after the uptick rule was put in place. There need to be a method for calculating growth rates that is not subject to fluctuation in the daily close values. All of the data must be used to calculate growth rates to eliminate temporary fluctuations in growth rates.

¹⁰ The formula for the annual rate of growth is $[r = (A / P)^{1/n} - 1]$, where P is the Principal or beginning value, r is the growth rate, n is the # of years between measurements, and A is the Amount at the end of n years.

A method that uses all of the data available is possible by using exponential growth rates and Ordinary Least Squares regression (OLS). The growth rate can be calculated with OLS by taking the natural log of the daily close as the dependent variable and the years from the beginning date as the independent variable. The formula for the continuous growth rate (r) is $[A = P * e^{rn}]$, where P is the beginning Principal, r is the growth rate, n is the # of years, and A is the Amount and the end of n years. The data was split into two sample periods. The period before the uptick rule was from May 27, 1896 to February 5th, 1938, and the period during the uptick rule was from February 6th, 1938 to July 5th, 2007. The results of the OLS regression of the growth rates are shown in Table 2.

The growth rate of the DOW during the period before the uptick rule was .026, or 2.6%. The growth rate of the DOW during the period when the uptick rule was in place was .065 or 6.5%. The ratio between the rates is 2.5 to 1. This means that there was a 150% increase in the rate of growth in the DOW when the uptick rule was in place. The probability that one would get a 6.5% rate of return without the uptick rule was found to be 1.04×10^{-54} . In a separate regression equation calculating the effect of years on the closing value of the DOW, and the change in rate due to the uptick rule added as a dummy variable, the t value for the uptick rule, coded as a 1, was -93.396. The confidence intervals shown were calculated at one billion to one odds. It is safe to say that these are significantly different rates, and that the growth in the DOW is substantially higher with the uptick rule than without.

Table 2: Growth Rate in Daily DOW Close by Year for Periods Before and During Uptick Rule

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	99.99999999% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Before Uptick Rule	-45.486	.444567		-102.316	.000	-48.515	-42.457
	.026	.000232	.711	112.505	.000	.025	.028
During Uptick Rule	-121.914	.232143		-525.169	.000	-123.496	-120.333
	.065	.000118	.972	554.708	.000	.064	.066

Conclusion

In this quick test, it would appear that the steady gain hypothesis is supported and the overpricing hypothesis is not. This confirmation of the steady gain hypothesis provides an additional set of analyses that confirm that the SEC results are not a short term anomaly. These results indicate that stock trading will be two to three times more profitable with the uptick rule than without it. The problem with a lack of theory to explain a steady gain still remains.

Both data sets provide almost identical results. The percentage gain in the DOW with the uptick rule was 4.37% higher per year with the uptick rule than without it. The SEC experiment had suggested that the stock market would be 4.78% more profitable with the uptick rule than without it. While this could be a coincidence, this seems unlikely.

The current U.S. market capitalization of 12 Trillion dollars is the basis from which the estimated gain from price restrictions can be calculated. A 4.37% annual gain amounts to 4.37% of 12 Trillion dollars, or 520 Billion dollars per year. This means that, if historic patterns are repeated now that the uptick rule is removed, the stock market is losing half of a Trillion dollars per year due to the removal of the uptick rule. In the four year period since the removal of the uptick rule, over two Trillion dollars could be expected to have been lost.

These figures seem incredibly large, and they indicate a free lunch of gargantuan proportions could be had through the simple act of reinstating the uptick rule. In searching for a theory to explain the differences in income to be obtained through price restrictions on short selling, it must be remembered that the daily loss is incredibly small and essentially unnoticeable. The daily losses due to the removal of the uptick rule are so small that they are almost statistically insignificant. It is only through the magnifying lens of time and the net effect of small changes on thousands of stocks that any differences are visible. The odds are greater than one billion to one that the price restrictions provided by the uptick rule will become permanent gains.